

A STUDY ON FINANCIAL PERFORMANCE OF SELECTED FERTILIZER COMPANIES IN INDIA

Mr. R. Senthilkumar Part-Time Ph.D Research Scholar, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Erode Arts & Science College, Erode.

Dr. M. Hajera Banu Assistant Professor, PG and Research Department of Commerce, Erode Arts & Science College, Erode.

ABSTRACT

Agriculture is the backbone of India in terms of their contribution in the growth and GDP directly or indirectly. It is the prevalent segment of economic activity in India, which imparts, raw materials and food most of all remarkably, the employment to a very huge section of population. Agriculture accounts for nearly one-fourth of India's GDP and more importantly about two-third of the country's population is dependent on agriculture for their livelihood. Agriculture contributes more than 18.5 percent of the Gross Domestic Product of the country. Successive five-year plans have laid emphasis on self-sufficiency and self-reliance in food grain production and concerted efforts in this direction have resulted in substantial increase in agriculture production and productivity. The obstacle in the path of agricultural development is fragmentation of land, depletion of ground water, improper irrigation facilities, etc. The availability of land for agriculture is declining due to growing population and use of land for commercial purpose. The major problem which is being faced by our farmers is the declining land productivity with reduced crop yields.

INTRODUCTION

The fertilizer industry is one of the core sectors in India. Fertilizer is a crucial factor of present agriculture. Indian fertilizer industry's main objective is to ensure the supply of primary and secondary nutrients in the required quantities. Agricultural products are solely depends upon the availability of their right ingredients like Urea and Pesticides. The production of the fertilizer companies always depends upon the availability of the financial resources. We have analysed the availability of financial resources and their impact on the profitability. As a result of Green revolution there was a huge demand for fertilizers in India. The country has achieved 80% self-sufficiency in production capacity of Urea. Fertilizer along with other inputs plays a vital role in helping farmers to achieve their high level of production. The country has become self-reliant in food production over the years as the Government has been pursuing policies to increase the availability and consumption of fertilizers at affordable cost. India's per hectare consumption of fertilizer has come a long way, it was less than 1/4th of the global

average, and has increased tremendously at present making India the third most fertilizer producing country in the world. The Indian fertilizer market is projected to register a CAGR of 11.9% during the forecast period(2022-2027).

The impact of the coronavirus pandemic on the Indian fertilizer market is low, as the national government exempted this sector from lockdown restrictions. However, the sector faced challenges in a shortage of labour and raw materials, shipments were affected in the initial lockdown process. The government of India took measures to ensure fertilizers are available to the farmers in the midst of lockdown, which resulted in increased sales of fertilizers. India is the second-largest consumer of fertilizers globally, with an annual consumption of more than 55.0 million metric ton.

The Indian fertilizer market is a consolidated market with the presence of major players, such as Coromandel International Limited, Indian Farmers Fertilizer Cooperative (IFFCO), Fertilizers and Chemicals Travancore (FACT), Deepak Fertilizers Limited, and Chambal Fertilizers Limited, Chambal Fertilizers and Chemicals Limited among others. The market is fragmented with a mix of government-owned and co-operatives garnering a high market share. While NFL is the largest government corporation in the fertilizer sector. Private companies engage in a high degree of product innovation to tap the non-subsidy space.

STATEMENT OF THE PROBLEM

Plants need a combination of nutrients to survive, and multiple types of fertilizer provide different inputs. In today's fertilizer sector there exists a major problem of pricing. Initially there is high pricing of raw materials which make it difficult for production which in turn make domestic production merely impossible. Secondly, since domestic production does not take place, the companies are more reliant on imports from other countries which increase the product cost above the affordable line. In this study, measures have been taken to check the impact of the rising prices of fertilizers on the overall profitability, efficiency and liquidity position of the selected fertilizer companies.

OBJECTIVES OF THE STUDY

- To access the liquidity position of selected fertilizer companies.
- To analyze the profitability position of selected fertilizer companies.
- To evaluate the operational efficiency of selected fertilizer companies.

NEED AND SCOPE OF STUDY

Fertilizer plays an extremely important role in increasing agricultural production. It continues to be the most important input, next to water in agricultural production. Fertilizer is required in increasing quantities to enable to feed the teeming millions in our Country. The Performance Appraisal programme enables the management to operate the business organization more effectively. It helps to identify the weaker spots of a company's operations and to take corrective action. Furthermore, it tends to restrain management as they are under pressure to maintain a favourable financial position.

The present study is done to evaluate the financial performance appraisal of selected fertilizer companies. i.e., **Coromandal Fertilizers Company, Chambal Fertilizers, and National Fertilizers Limited**. It tries to find out the profitability and the operational efficiency of these fertilizer companies. The scope of this study, can be extended to the future investors who decide to invest in this particular sector.

RESEARCH METHEDODOLOGY

RESEARCH DESIGN

The study is undertaken to analyse the financial performance of 3 fertilizer companies (i.e.,) Coramandal Fertilisers Limited, Chambal Fertilizers and Chemicals Limited and National Fertilisers Limited. Also to make a comparative analysis based on their profitability, liquidity and solvency level.

The study used Descriptive Research Design for the purpose of getting an insight over the companies. It is used with the objective to provide a systematic description that is as factual and accurate as possible.

TOOLS USED FOR THE STUDY

✓RATIO ANALYSIS

• Liquidity Ratio

- i. Current Ratio
- ii. Liquid Ratio

• Profitability Ratio

- i. Gross Profit Ratio
- ii. Net Profit Ratio

SOURCE OF DATA

The study depends upon Secondary source of data. Secondary data is the data that has already been collected through primary sources and made readily available in the firm's internal records and publications. It is a type of data that has already been collected in the past. The secondary data for this study is collected from the annual report of the companies. Various articles and journals related to the companies have also been reviewed for the purpose.

PERIOD OF DATA COLLECTION

The study has been undertaken for a period of 5 years from 2018-19 to 2022-23.

LIMITATIONS

- The study is limited to a time period of last 5 years.
- The study is completely dependent upon secondary data i.e., data published in the annual reports of the companies' websites.
- Only limited ratios have been used for the study.

REVIEW OF LITERATURE

A literature review is an overview of the previously published works on a specific topic. A literature review is supposed to provide with a general image of the existing knowledge on the topic under question. The main objective of analysing literature is to find out the unexplored areas of past literatures and an attempt has been made to cover those areas in the current study.

Gargi Patel (2019) "A Comparative Study of Financial Performance of IFFCO and KRIBHCO". The main purpose of the study is to know the efficiency and performance of IFFCO and KRIBHCO for the period of last 5 years from 2011-12 to 2015-16. The study is mainly based on secondary data and the required data is collected from annual published reports of selected units IFFCO and KRIBHCO, various periodicals related to current ratio, quick ratio, return on net worth and debt equity ratio are used for the analysis and interpretation. The study concludes that, ratios of both the companies show almost equal Financial performance, but with IFFCO having a slightly higher edge when compared to KRIBHCO.

Vyas Krishna Ashutoshbhai (2020) "A Comparative Evaluation of corporate performance of selected fertilizers in India". The study focuses on the comparison of the corporate performance of selected Public sector and Private sector Fertilizers in India for the 5 years starting from 2015-16 to 2019-20. The evaluation of corporate performance was carried out

through selected profitability, liquidity and management efficiency ratios.

K.N. Chavda & Prof.Mehul B.Shah (2015) “A Financial Ratio analysis of Gujarat Narmada valley fertiliser & chemicals Ltd”. The study was undertaken with the help of statistical analysis, the forecasting of the financial performance of subsequent years of the company was made for particular item such as sales, inventory, profit, etc in order to perceive various ratios such as the various profitability ratios and the liquidity ratios. In accordance with the study, GNFC limited has a sound financial position, excluding the current ratio which is barely unsatisfactory at the company.

Aisha Masood (2014) “An empirical study of financial performance offertiliser sector of Pakistan listed on KSE-100: A comparative Analysis In this study, the financial soundness and performance of the Fertilizer Sector in which 7 companies for a period of 4 years starting from 2010 to 2013 . In order to build the relationship and set up a platform for comparison various types of ratios such as solvency, liquidity, activity, profitability and market ratios are used. From the study it can be concluded that among all the companies the Fauji group of companies namely Fauji Fertilizers Limited and Fauji Bin Qasim Fertilizers Limited have maintained a sound financial position in the market.

Dr. Prameela S. Shetty (2012) “Performance of Fertilizer industry in India”. The purpose of this study was to understand the growth of fertilizer industry in India. For the study, financial data of 60 out of 76 companies were collected for a period of 10 years (2000 – 2009). This study was based on ratio analysis, T test, L Test tools to analyse the performance of companies according to their study, it was found that there is no significant difference between the performance of those companies. All the companies performed equally well.

ANALYSIS AND INTERPRETATION

The term ‘financial analysis’, also known as analysis and interpretation of financial statements’, refers to the process of determining financial strengths and weaknesses of the firm by establishing strategic relationship between the items of the balance sheet, profit and loss account and other operative data.

The primary objective of financial statement analysis is to understand and diagnose the information contained in financial statement with a view to judge the profitability and financial soundness of the firm, and to make forecast about future prospects of the firm.

RATIO ANALYSIS

Ratio Analysis is done to analyze the Company's financial and trend of the company's result over years.

LIQUIDITY RATIOS

Liquidity ratios are an important class of financial metrics used to determine a debtor's ability to pay off current debt obligations without raising external capital.

CURRENT RATIO

The current ratio is a liquidity ratio that measures a company's ability to pay short-term obligations or those due within one year. It tells investors and analysts how a company can maximize the current assets on its balance sheet to satisfy its current debt and other payables. A current ratio that is in line with the industry average or slightly higher is generally considered acceptable. A current ratio that is lower than the industry average may indicate a higher risk of distress or default. Similarly, if a company has a very high current ratio compared with its peer group, it indicates that management may not be using its assets efficiently.

$$\text{Current Ratio} = \frac{\text{Current Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

CURRENT RATIO

YEAR	COROMANDEL	NFL	CHAMBAL
2019	1.22	1.12	1.14
2020	1.25	1.15	1.18
2021	1.23	1.11	1.02
2022	1.44	1.03	1.1
2023	1.95	1.07	2.06

The above table shows the current ratio analysis of the 3 selected fertilizer companies for the study period. In our analysis Coromandel fertilizers has maintained a satisfactory level of current ratio in 5 years. This means that the company is highly capable to pay off its short-term obligation. Chambal Fertiliser Limited, has topped with the highest current ratio of 2.06 in the year 2023. However the company has exceeded the satisfactory level between 1.2 -2. It indicates that the company is unable to use its current assets efficiently. The Lowest C/R among 3 companies is also obtained by Chambal with the ratio of 1.02 in 2023 and NFL with 1.03 in 2022. This means that these companies

may have problems in meeting their short term obligations.

LIQUID RATIO OR QUICK RATIO

The quick ratio represents the extent to which a business can pay its short-term obligations with its most liquid assets. In other words, it measures the proportion of a business's current liabilities that it can meet with cash and assets that can be readily converted to cash. The quickratio is also known as the acid test ratio, a reference to the fact that it's used to measure the financial strength of a business. A business with a negative quick ratio is considered more likely to struggle in a crisis, whereas one with a positive quick ratio is more likely to survive.

$$\text{Liquid Ratio} = \frac{\text{Liquid Assets}}{\text{Current Liabilities}}$$

TABLE SHOWING THE LIQUID RATIO

YEAR	COROMANDEL	NFL	CHAMBAL
2017	0.91	1.01	0.94
2018	0.9	1.03	0.93
2019	0.77	0.93	0.81
2020	0.94	0.9	0.93
2021	1.17	0.94	1.54

The above table shows that the liquid ratio analysis of the 3 selected fertilizer companies for the study period. In our analysis, Chambal Fertilizer Limited has inflated with the highest liquid ratio of 1.54 in the year 2023. This entails that the company is being capable to easily liquidate its Assets in order to pay its short term debts. Among the 3 companies Coromandel Fertilizer Company and NFL has resulted with a sunken liquid ratio of 0.77 in 2021 and 0.9 in the year of 2022 respectively. A low liquid ratio means that these companies may have numerous bills and poor collection of account receivables.

PROFITABILITY RATIOS

Profitability ratios are a class of financial metrics that are used to assess a business's ability to generate earnings relative to its revenue, operating costs, balance sheet assets, or shareholders' equity over time, using data from a specific point in time.

GROSS PROFIT RATIO

Gross Profit Margin Ratio, sometimes also referred to as gross margin, is a type of profitability ratio. It helps to measure how much profit a company makes from the sale of goods and services after deducting the direct costs. In simple words, it is a simple

metric to measure the company's profitability. Also, it helps to evaluate how efficiently the company is using its labour and raw materials during the production process.

$$\text{Gross Profit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Gross Profit}}{\text{Net Sales or total revenue}} \times 100$$

GROSS PROFIT RATIO

YEAR	COROMANDEL	NFL	CHAMBAL
2019	6.99	4.24	8.3
2020	9.12	3.75	9.65
2021	8.22	3.76	7.85
2022	10.45	2	10.86
2023	12.47	2.78	15.4

The above table shows that the Gross Profit ratio analysis of the 3 selected fertilizer companies for the study period. In our analysis Chambal Fertilizer Limited, has the highest Gross profit ratio of 15.4 in the year 2023. A higher gross profit margin indicates that Chambal fertilisers is having a proportionate increase on sales price when compared to cost of goods sold. The stunted Gross profit ratio among the 3 companies is obtained by NFL with a ratio of 2 in 2022. NFL with a low gross margin might result in less money available to cover the operating costs of the business. The Ideal gross profit value of 7% to 10% is met by Coromandel and Chambal fertilizers throughout the study period.

NET PROFIT RATIO

The net profit percentage is the ratio of after-tax profits to net sales. It reveals the remaining profit after all costs of production, administration, and financing have been deducted from sales, and income taxes recognized. As such, it is one of the best measures of the overall results of a firm, especially when combined with an evaluation of how well it is using its working capital. The measure is commonly reported on a trend line, to judge performance over time. It is also used to compare the results of a business with its competitors.

$$\text{Net Profit Ratio} = \frac{\text{Net Income}}{\text{Net Sales or total revenue}} \times 100$$

NET PROFIT RATIO

YEAR	COROMANDEL	NFL	CHAMBAL
2019	4.68	2.71	5.72
2020	6	2.38	6.38
2021	5.41	2.41	5.4
2022	8.07	1.38	10.03
2023	9.27	1.99	10.59

The above table shows the Net Profit ratio analysis of the 3 selected fertilizer companies for the study period. In our analysis Chambal Fertilizer Limited, has mounted with the highest Net profit ratio of 10.59 in the year of 2023. This Indicates that Chambal fertilisers is able to effectively control its operating expenses and efficiently converts its revenue into actual profit. NFL has obtained depressed net profit ratio of 1.38 in 2022 among its peer group companies. The ideal net profit ratio of above 10% is obtained only by Chambal fertilisers in the year 2020 and 2023.

FINDINGS, SUGGESTIONS AND CONCLUSION

FINDINGS

- The current ratio of Coromandel Fertilizer Company is highest in the year 2023 with ratio of 1.95 and lowest with 1.22 in 2019.
- NFL has its highest current ratio of 1.15 in 2020 and lowest of 1.03 in the year 2022.
- Chambal Fertilizer Limited has the lowest Current Ratio of 1.02 in 2021 and highest of 2.06 in 2023.
- The liquidity ratio for Coromandel Fertilizer Company is more immense in the year 2023 with a ratio of 1.17 and stunted with 0.77 in 2020.
- The NFL has its accumulated liquid ratio of 1.03 in 2020 and lowered 0.9 in the year of 2022.
- Chambal Fertilizer Limited has raised the liquid ratio of 1.54 in 2023 and deficit of 0.81 in 2021.
- The Gross profit ratio for Coromandel Fertilizer Company is maximized in the year 2023 with a ratio of 12.47 and depleted with 6.99 in 2019.
- The NFL has its increased Gross profit ratio of 4.24 in 2019 and lowered 2 in the year of 2022.
- Chambal Fertilizer Limited has raised the gross profit ratio of 15.4 in 2023 and lowest

of 7.85 in 2019.

- The Net profit ratio for Coromandel Fertilizer Company is topped in the year 2023 with a ratio of 9.27 and depressed with 4.68 in 2019.
- The NFL has its raised Net profit ratio of 2.71 in 2019 and deficit 1.38 in the year of 2022.
- Chambal Fertilizer Limited has inflated the Net profit ratio of 10.59 in 2023 and depleted 5.4 in 2021.

SUGGESTIONS

- In Today's fast growing economy agriculture plays a vital role in contributing a major part in the GDP of India. The fertilizer industry is the main key factor in every agriculture produce.
- The fertilizer companies have to develop innovations in their products to find out solutions for problems in usage of fertilizers for different crops. The R and D department of these companies has to be strengthened by constant study and updation of fertilizers to know the optimum quantity of fertilizer needed for effective growth of crops. Also, the R and D must indulge in the development and promotion of bio fertilizers as there is a positive shift from chemical fertilizers to bio fertilizers in today's market.
- Innovation is always the reason for a fast-developing sector. The development of new products in the fertilizer industry must reach each and every farmer. The companies must involve in product promotion activities through platforms like FM and also run awareness programs in rural areas to educate the farmers on the technologies and new products available. This will not only lead to higher yield but will give the company higher sales as well.
- The leading fertilizer companies must contemplate domestic production. The industry needs to be self-reliant and not depend on import of fertilizers. In this way we can escape the vagaries of high volatility in international prices. Domestic production would bring the prices down which would be affordable for all farmers. This would result in higher sales for the companies.
- The Indian agriculture sector consists of mostly small-scale farmers. Fertilizer Companies should provide their products in smaller packages for those cultivating their crops on small portions of land rather than having only mass quantity packaging. This would pave way for small scale farmers to buy limited amount of fertilizer required by them. This enables the fertilizer industry to diversify their product line to a wide range

of peasant.

- The government needs to extend the NBS model to urea and allow for price rationalization of urea when compared to non-nitrogenous fertilizers. This will in turn cut down the surplus production of urea and also would help in reducing the fertilizer subsidy.

CONCLUSION

Ahead of kharif sowing, due to begin next month, India faces the challenge of meeting its requirement of fertilizers, the supply of which has been disrupted in the wake of Russia's invasion of Ukraine. Also, the pandemic has impacted fertilizer production, import and transportation across the world during the last two years. In this current scenario, fertilizer industries as a whole are in financially distress state. Going by the ownership pattern, privately owned companies like Coromandel Fertilizers Ltd and Chambal Fertilizers and Chemicals Ltd exercised better financial operations while comparing to a Government Company like National Fertilizers Ltd(NFL). NFL fared poorly and the best performing company was Chambal. The fertilizer industry is predicted to have a CAGR of 11.9% during 2024-29. In the study, an attempt has been made to comprehend various ratios that are used to determine the financial stability of the selected fertilizer companies.

BIBLIOGRAPHY

WEBSITES:

- <https://www.coromandel.biz>
- <https://www.chambalfertilisers.com>
- <https://www.nationalfertiliozers.com>
- <https://en.wikipedia.org>
- <https://www.economictimes.indiatimes.com>